

JAVASCRIPT OPERATORLARI

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301 - MI guruh talabasi

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7943517>

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tezida JavaScript dasturlash tili operatorlari va ularning ifoda va shartlarni yaratishdagi roli muhokama qilinadi. Biz har xil turdagi ma'lumotlarga ega operatorlarning ishlash xususiyatlarini va ulardan turli vaziyatlarda foydalanishni o'rganamiz. Operatorlardan foydalanishda yuzaga kelishi mumkin bo'lgan xatolar va ularni oldini olish yo'llari ham ko'rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: JavaScript, operatorlar, ifodalar, mantiq, shartlar.

JavaScript - bu asosan veb-saytlar va veb-ilovalarni yaratish uchun ishlatiladigan dasturlash tili. Operatorlar JavaScript dasturlash tilining muhim elementi hisoblanadi, chunki ular ma'lumotlar ustida turli amallarni bajarishga va muayyan operatsiyalarni bajarish uchun sharoit yaratishga imkon beradi.

JavaScript- da bir necha turdagi bayonotlar mavjud, masalan:

Arifmetik operatorlar Arifmetik operatorlar matematik amallarni bajarish uchun ishlatiladi. JavaScript -da quyidagi arifmetik operatorlar mavjud: qo'shish (+), ayirish (-), ko'paytirish (*), bo'lish (/) va modul (%). Masalan:

```
let x =5;
```

```
let y =2;
```

```
console . log ( x + y ); // natija: 7
```

```
console . log ( x - y ); // natija: 3
```

```
console . log ( x * y ); // natija: 10
```

```
console . log ( x / y ); // natija: 2.5
```

```
console . log ( x % y ); // natija: 1
```

Taqqoslash operatorlari Taqqoslash operatorlari qiymatlarni solishtirish uchun ishlatiladi. JavaScript -da quyidagi taqqoslash operatorlari mavjud: teng (==), teng emas (!=), qat'iy tenglik (===), qat'iy tengsizlik (!==), katta (>), kichik (<), dan katta yoki teng (>=) va kichik yoki teng (<=). Masalan:

```
let x = 5 bo'lsin ;
```

```
let y = 2 bo'lsin ;
```

```
console.log(x == y) ; // natija : noto'g'ri
```

```
console.log( x != y); // natija : rost
```

```
console.log(x === '5'); // natija : noto'g'ri
```

```
console. log( x !== '5'); // natija : rost
```

```
console logi ( x > y ) ; // natija : rost
```

```
console logi ( x < y ) ; // natija : noto'g'ri
```

```
console.log(x >= y) ; // natija : rost
```

```
console.log(x <= y) ; // natija : noto'g'ri
```

Mantiqiy operatorlar Mantiqiy operatorlar shartlarni ulash uchun ishlatiladi. JavaScript- da quyidagi mantiqiy operatorlar mavjud: AND operatori (&&), OR operatori (||) va NOT operatori (!). Masalan:

```
let x = 5 bo'lsin ;
let y = 2 bo'lsin ;
console.log(x > 3 && y < 4) ; // natija : rost
console.log(x > 3 || y > 4) ; // natija : rost
console.log(!(x > 3)); // natija : noto'g'ri
```

O'stirish va kamaytirish operatorlari: o'sish va kamaytirish operatorlari o'zgaruvchining qiymatini 1 ga oshirish yoki kamaytirish uchun ishlatiladi. quyidagi oshirish va kamaytirish operatorlari JavaScript da mavjud : oshirish (++) va kamaytirish (--). Masalan :

```
let x = 5 bo'lsin ;
console.log(x++); // natija : 5
console.log(x); // natija: 6
console.log(++x); // natija: 7
console.log(x-); // natija: 7
console.log(x); // natija: 6
console.log(--x); // natija : 5
```

Shartli (uchlik) operator Shartli operator (uchlik operator) kodning bir qatorida shartlar yaratish uchun ishlatiladi. U quyidagi sintaksisga ega: shart ? qiymat1: qiymat2. Agar shart rost bo'lsa, qiymat1 qaytariladi, aks holda qiymat2 qaytariladi. Masalan:

```
let yosh = 25;
let status = yosh >= 18 bo'lsin ? " Voyaga etgan " : " Voyaga etmagan ";
console.log(holat); // natija: "kattalar"
```

JavaScript tilidagi operatorlar dasturlashda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Operatorlardan to'g'ri foydalanish kodni soddalashtirish va uning samaradorligini oshirish imkonini beradi.

Xulosa

Ushbu tezisda biz JavaScript dasturlash tilining arifmetik, taqqoslash operatorlari, mantiqiy operatorlar, belgilash operatorlari, oshirish va kamaytirish operatorlari, uchlik operatorlari kabi asosiy operatorlarini ko'rib chiqdik . Biz ularning sintaksisi va qo'llanilishini o'rganib chiqdik va ularning dasturlashdagi rolini muhokama qildik.

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